

A fodder conservation technology in cold arid region of Ladakh, India

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Abstract

Silage is a fermented feed resulting from preservation method based on natural lactic acid fermentation under anaerobic conditions. Ensiling is a suitable and promising technique for preserving fresh forage with minimal losses which ensures animal feed availability during dry or winter season. Ensiling technology has increased the feeding value of silages. This process is based on lactic acid fermentation under anaerobiosis which preserves the forage in high nutritional value.

Keywords: Silage; Alfa-Alfa; High Altitude; Fermented Technology; Probiotics

Introduction

Silage is a fermented feed resulting from preservation method based on natural lactic acid fermentation under anaerobic conditions (Gollop et al., 2005). Silage can be defined as any plant material that has undergone fermentation or “pickling” in a silo. Very different plant materials can be used for ensiling: grass, clover, alfalfa, barley, corn, wheat, sorghum (Ashbell and Weinberg, 2006) and various moist “by-products” of the food industry, such as apple pomace, beet pulp and brewer’s mash (Ajila et al., 2012). The main purpose of ensiling is to keep forage available throughout the year for use as the main source of feed with high nutritional value for ruminants, thus improving the economic and environmental sustainability of production systems. The most important crops for ensiling are whole crop corn, alfalfa and various grasses (Weinberg and Ashbell, 2003).

The ensiling process is defined as involving the

following steps: harvesting of crop at the optimal stage of maturity, chopping, loading into a silo, compacting and sealing to exclude air, storing, and finally unloading for animal feeding. The four processing steps at which biochemical and microbiological incidents can arise are the aerobic, fermentation, storage and unloading stages (Ashbell and Weinberg, 2006). Fig. 1 summarizes the theoretical evolution of the main physico-chemical values and microbial populations in well-processed silage.

Aerobic phase:

The aerobic phase of ensiling begins at harvest, continues during wilting and for several hours after filling the silos and sealing the silo. At this stage, pH and oxygen are at their highest levels. Biomass respiration occurs for several hours, consuming sugars and producing carbon dioxide and water, until all oxygen is depleted. Plant proteases and amino acidases catabolize true protein, which will result in increased levels of non-protein nitrogen (Ohyama, 1970).

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Anaerobic fermentation phase:

At this stage oxygen is depleted and CO₂ accumulates. Plant enzymes as well as aerobic organisms may be inhibited. Aerobic microorganisms are replaced by anaerobic and facultative microbes. Three main types of bacteria lactic acid bacteria (LAB), enterobacteria and clostridia capable of anaerobic growth begin to proliferate and compete for the available organic matter. In a normal desired fermentation, LAB dominates other microorganisms as they produce lactic acid from water-soluble carbohydrates. The accumulation of lactic acid is the main reason behind the rapid decrease of silage pH to 4.0-4.5 (Winters et al., 2000). The fermentation phase can last for up to four weeks (Mustafa and Seguin, 2003c) and during this phase temperature, O₂ and pH will be at their lowest.

Stabilization phase:

At this stage, pH has dropped to approximately 4.0-4.5, all microorganisms found in the silage are inhibited including the LAB and most of metabolic activity has stopped. This phase will last until the silo is opened and silage is exposed to air.

Feed-out phase:

During this phase, silos are opened and silages, which were previously kept under oxygen-free

conditions are exposed to oxygen. The presence of oxygen initiates the activity of undesirable microflora such as yeast, moulds and acetic acid bacteria. These microorganisms grow on residual substrates and fermentation products. The main indications of this deterioration are the production of heat and carbon dioxide due to respiration, and reduction in lactic acid concentration reflected in a pH increase.

End products of silage fermentation

The end products of fermentation reflect the type of microorganisms that dominate during the ensiling process and can be used to assess the quality of the silage. Presence of lactate as an end product reflects fermentation by homo fermentative lactic acid bacteria. A mixture of lactate and acetate indicate heterofermentative lactic acid bacteria dominance whereas butyrate and ammonia reflect undesirable clostridial activity (McDonald et al., 1991). Ammonia N can also arise from the action of plant enzymes and enterobacteria and the reduction of nitrates and nitrites (McDonald et al., 1991).

During fermentation, silage microorganisms catabolize water-soluble carbohydrates mostly to organic acids and some alcohol. The main sugars present in the water-soluble carbohydrates fraction of legume forages are fructose, glucose and sucrose (McDonald et al., 1991). Possible fermentation end products of different sugars by different types of bacteria are shown in Table 1.

Micro-organism	Substrate	End product
<i>Homofermentative Lactic Acid Bacteria</i>	1 glucose 1 fructose 1 pentose (xylose, arabinose)	2 lactate 2 lactate 1 lactate + 1 acetate
<i>Heterofermentative Lactic Acid Bacteria</i>	1 glucose 1 fructose 3 fructose 1 glucose + 2 fructose 1 pentose	1 lactate + 1 ethanol + 1 CO ₂ 1 lactate + 1 ethanol + 1 CO ₂ 2 mannitol + 1 lactate + 1 acetate + 1 CO ₂ 2 mannitol + 1 lactate + 1 acetate + 1 CO ₂ 1 lactate + 1 acetate
<i>Sacharolytic Clostridia</i>	1 glucose 2 lactate	1 butyrate + 2 CO ₂ 1 butyrate + 2 CO ₂
<i>Yeasts</i>	1 glucose	2 ethanol + 2 CO ₂

Table 2: Microbial species isolated from silages.		
Botanical description	Plant characters	
Lactic acid bacteria		
<i>Enterococcus flavescens</i>	Maize	Brusetti et al., 2006
<i>Enterococcus mundti</i>	Maize stover	Pang et al., 2011b
<i>Lactobacillus acetotolerans</i>	Maize	Li and nishino 2011b
<i>Lactobacillus panis</i>	Maize	Li and nishino 2011b
<i>Lactobacillus reuteri</i>	Maize	Li and nishino 2011b
<i>Lactobacillus taiwanensis</i>		Wang et al., 2009
<i>Lactobacillus zeae</i>	Lucerne	Rossi and dellaglio 2007
<i>Leuconostoc lactis</i>	Maize stover	Pang et al., 2011b
<i>Paralactbacillus selangorensis</i>	Italian ryegrass	Parvin et al., 2010
<i>Pediococcus dextrinicus</i>	Italian ryegrass	Pang et al., 2011b
<i>Pediococcus parvulus</i>	Maize	Li et al., 2011
<i>Weissella cibaria</i>	Maize, maize stover	Pang et al., 2011a, b
<i>Weissella kimchii</i>	Maize	Brusetti et al., 2006
<i>Weissella paramesenteriodes</i>	Maize	Li et al., 2011
Anaerobic spore former's		
<i>Clostridium baratii</i>	Maize	Rossi and dellaglio 2007
<i>Paenibacillus macerans</i>	Maize	Rossi and dellaglio 2007
Bacillus		
<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	Maize	Brusetti et al., 2006
Enterobacteria		
<i>Erwinia persicina</i>	Italian ryegrass	Li and nishino 2011a
<i>Pantoea agglomerans</i>	Italian ryegrass	Li and nishino 2011a
<i>Rahnella aquatilis</i>	Italian ryegrass	Li and nishino 2011a
Acetic acid bacteria		
<i>Acetobacter pasteurianus</i>	Maize	Li and nishino 2011b
Fungi		
<i>Candida apicola</i>	Maize, Italian ryegrass	Rossi and dellaglio 2007
<i>Candida intermedia</i>	Maize	Li et al., 2011
<i>Candida mesenterica</i>	Maize	Rossi and dellaglio 2007
<i>Candida quercitrusa</i>	Maize	Li et al., 2011
<i>Saccharomyces martiniae</i>	Maize	Li et al., 2011
<i>Pichia deserticola</i>	Maize	Li et al., 2011
<i>Pichia fermentans</i>	Maize	Rossi and dellaglio 2007
<i>Pichia kudriavzevil</i>	Maize	Li et al., 2011
<i>Penicillium sp.</i>	Maize	Roigr et al., 2009
<i>Fusarium sp.</i>	Maize	Roigr et al., 2009
<i>Aspergillus sp.</i>	Maize	Roigr et al., 2009

Table 3: Silage fermentation stages and their mechanisms (Mohd-Setapara et al., 2012).

Stages	Phases name	Time taken	Mechanisms
1	Aerobic	2 days	Breakdown of plants protein and reduce to amino acids.
2	Anaerobic fermentation	2-3 days	Growth and development of acetic acid.
3	Brings Phase 2 to and end	3-4 days	Enhances the growth and development of anaerobic group of bacteria and produces lactic acid.
4	Lactic acid formation	4-21 days	Lactic acid begin to increase until pH is low enough to inhibit growth of bacteria.
5	Material Storage	21 days	Large population of bacteria may grow and produce butyric acid instead of lactic acid.
6	Aerobic decomposition	Starts as soon as silage exposed to air	High population growth of yeast or mold. Proper management is vital.

Micro-organisms involved in the ensiling process

Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) play a fundamental role in silage fermentation and can also influence silage quality (Lin et al., 1992). Members of this group compete for available nutrients with undesirable in the ensiling process microorganisms. Following are the microorganisms involved in the ensiling process.

Lactic acid bacteria

Lactic acid bacteria belong to the epiphytic microorganisms which occur on the forage crops and grasses (McDonald et al., 1991). Lactic acid bacteria usually found living in association with silage belong to the genera *Lactobacillus*, *Pediococcus*, *Leuconostoc*, and *Enterococcus* (McDonald et al., 1991). The majority of silage lactic acid bacteria grow best at mesophilic temperatures (between 20 and 40 °C), having an optimum around 30 °C. A distinctive feature of the lactic acid bacteria is their acid tolerance. They are able to decrease the silage pH to about 4 to 5, depending on the species and the type of forage crop. All lactic acid bacteria are facultative aerobes, but some have a preference for anaerobic conditions.

Based on their sugar metabolism, lactic acid bacteria are

classified as homofermentative, and heterofermentative species. Homofermentative species produce more than 85% lactic acid from hexoses such as glucose. They are considered as desirable LAB in the silage fermentation process as it rapidly producing lactic acid and lowering the final pH to preserve nutrients by inhibiting plant enzyme and undesirable microorganisms (Schmidt and Kung 2010; Tabacoo et al., 2011). On the other hand, in the heterofermentative process, the final fermentation product is lactic acid, ethanol and CO₂. However, fermentation characteristics and aerobic stability of inoculated silage have been enhanced by combinations of homofermentative and heterofermentative LAB (Adesogan and Salawu, 2004; Filya, 2003a) or homofermentative LAB with propionic acid bacteria (Filya et al., 2006).

Several novel species have been isolated and characterized from silage which includes *Lactobacillus taiwanensis* (Wang et al., 2009), *Pediococcus lolii* (Doi et al., 2009) and *Lactobacillus nasuensis* sp. (Cai et al., 2012). Yang et al., 2010 studied on natural populations of lactic acid bacteria (LAB) and silage fermentation of vegetable residues. Based on 16S rDNA gene sequence analysis, *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *Lactococcus piscium*, *Lactococcus lactis*, *Leuconostoc citreum*, *Weissella soli* and *Leuconostoc gelidum* were identified. Pang et al., 2012 reported that *Leuconostoc*

pseudomesenteroides, *Lactococcus lactis* subsp. *lactis*, *Lactobacillus brevis*, and *Weissella paramesenteroides* were dominant members of the LAB population on several forage crops and silages.

Lactobacillus hilgardii strains UFLA SIL51 and UFLA SIL52 from sugar cane silage were used as starter cultures for sugar cane silage resulted in silage with the best characteristics in relation to DM loss, low ethanol content, higher LAB population, and low butyric acid content (Avila et al., 2014). Ni et al., 2015 have identified *Lactobacillus plantarum* subsp. *plantarum* (8.1%), *L. casei* (5.1%), *Leuconostoc pseudomesenteroides* (11.1%), *Pediococcus pentosaceus* (24.2%), *Enterococcus mundtii* (12.1%), *Lactococcus garvieae* (15.2%), *E. faecium* (9.1%) strains from paddy rice silage in China. *Lactobacillus plantarum* and *L. casei* are the dominant species from Guinea grass and Napier grass and could grow at lower pH and produce more lactic acid than the other isolates (Khota et al., 2016).

Enterobacteria

Enterobacteria are defined as Gram-negative, non-sporulating, usually motile, facultative anaerobic rod-shaped bacteria. They belong to the epiphytic microflora of most forage crops. During the pre-ensiling *Erwinia herbicola* and *Rahnella aquitilis* often dominate the fresh crop, but after ensiling these species are rapidly superseded by other species, such as *Hafnia alvei*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Serratia fonticola* (Heron et al., 1993). They occur in the early stages of silage fermentation and compete with the lactic acid bacteria for nutrients. They have weak proteolytic activity and are able to deaminate and decarboxylate some amino acids. These activities contribute to the formation of ammonia and biogenic amines in silage and resulting in degradation of silage quality (Van et al., 1997).

Clostridia

Butyric acid bacteria (BAB) found in silage come from soil or manure accidentally included with the plant material during silo filling (Rammer, 1996). They are able to convert lactic acid into butyric acid, hydrogen and carbon dioxide at a relatively low pH (Dunierrea et al., 2013). The main BAB found in silage are endospore forming

bacteria of the genera *Clostridium*, especially *C. tyrobutyricum* and *C. butyricum* (Driehuis and Oude Elferink, 2000; Pahlow et al., 2003). Clostridia are identified as Gram-positive, motile, rod-shaped bacteria, and obligate anaerobic bacteria. They are one of the most detrimental microorganisms involved in the fermentation process. Extensive growth of BAB can therefore induce a pH increase and the growth of less acid-tolerant spoilage microorganisms. Maize silage was found to be a more important source of BAB than grass silage in the Netherlands (Visser et al., 2007a).

Bacillus

Bacilli are endospore-forming aerobic or facultatively anaerobic bacteria. Facultative anaerobic bacilli can ferment a variety of carbohydrates and produce ethanol, glycerol, 2,3-butandiol and organic acids including lactate (McDonald et al., 1991). Species typically associated with silage are *Bacillus cereus*, *B. lentus*, *B. firmus*, *B. sphaericus*, *B. licheniformis*, and *B. polymyxa* (Woolford et al., 1978). Proliferation of bacilli usually occurs during the later stages of aerobic spoilage of silage (Lindgren et al., 1985). High numbers of bacillus spores have been detected in the surface layers of grass and maize silage (Vreman et al., 1999).

Yeasts and molds

Fungi are eukaryotic, heterotrophic microorganisms abundant in soil and on vegetation. They represent two major subgroups; moulds which grow mainly as multicellular, filamentous colonies and yeasts which grow mainly as single cells.

Yeasts are undesirable microorganisms found in silage as they are involved in aerobic spoilage either during the aerobic phase at the beginning of ensiling or during the unloading phase (Driehuis and Oude Elferink, 2000). Because of their high resistance to acidity and capability to assimilate lactic acid under aerobic conditions, yeasts are considered to be the primary causative microorganisms of aerobic spoilage in silage (Woolford, 1990). Courtin and Spoelstra (1990) have developed a mathematical model which validated the aerobic deterioration in grass and whole-crop corn silages initiated by yeast. Lactate-fermenting species such as *Candida* and *Hansenula* were reported to dominate in silages

after air penetrated silos (McDonald et al., 1991).

Many species of fungi have been isolated from different kind of silages, depending on crop or silage additives used (May et al., 2001; Li and Nishino, 2011c). The majorities of fungi are strict aerobes and can only be found in oxic areas such as near the outside of the silo or near the unloading face. A study on Brazilian corn silage samples showed that *Fusarium* sp. were the most frequent molds, followed by *Penicillium* sp., *Aspergillus* sp., *Trichosporon* sp., and *Cladosporium* sp. (Orsi et al., 2000). Many species of moulds such as *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium* and *Penicillium* produce mycotoxins (Oldenburg, 1991) and these mycotoxin producing fungi have been isolated from corn silage (Roigr et al., 2009). The undesirable effects of moulds mainly occur during the feed-out phase in the ensiling process when silage is exposed to air. Their role in aerobic deterioration of silages is usually associated with yeast growth. Moulds degrade a variety of substrates that can lead to complete decomposition of plant tissues which is highly undesirable in silage making.

Factors affecting the ensiling process

The ensiling of forage is a process where many variables influence the course and outcome of silage fermentation. The first is the nature of the raw material which is determined by the chemical and microbial composition of the crop. The second feature is related to ensiling condition imposed by the silage-maker, which include processes such as wilting, mechanical treatment of forage and use of additives.

Crops

Different crops possess a variable capability to complete a successful ensiling process. These capabilities express the ensilability of the crop. Weissbach et al. (1974) indicated that the effects of WSC concentration, DM content and buffering capacity of the crop could predict the ensilability of forage crops. The key is to estimate the correct amount of WSC needed to ensure a proper ensiling process in the crop at a given DM content and buffering capacity. In addition to these, variability in concentration of nitrate (Weissbach, 1996) and epiphytic microflora count (Muck, 1993b) in the crop have been seen to influence the ensiling process.

Water soluble carbohydrates in crop

One of the main factors influencing the ensilability of crops is the concentration of (water soluble carbohydrate) WSC in the crop. Glucose and fructose are the most important WSC and are the substrate for lactic acid bacteria at the earliest stages of ensiling process. The concentration of WSC in temperate forages often depends on the forage species and the stage of maturity. Among grasses grown in temperate zones, ryegrasses (*Lolium* spp.) have the highest WSC content, on average 175 g kg⁻¹ DM. The second most commonly grown grass, timothy (*Phleum* spp.), contains about 110 g WSC kg⁻¹ DM, and cocksfoot (*Dactylis glomerata*) that contains only 79 g WSC kg⁻¹ DM. The concentration of WSC in these grasses appears to increase during early development as the ratio of stem to leaves increases. The enhancement of WSC is related to the increase of the polysaccharide fructan in the stem tissues. Raguse and Smith (1966) analyzed WSC of alfalfa at the vegetative, pre-bud, mid-bud, early bloom, full-bloom and green seed pod stage. They found that WSC decreases as maturity advances with the highest level reported at the pre-bud stage (109 g kg⁻¹).

Crop dry matter

Wilting is performed to optimize forage dry matter content before ensiling. The DM content is an important factor influencing the microbial population and activity in the ensiled crop (McDonald et al., 1991). But, water content and availability in the crop are essential for microbial activity during the ensiling process. The availability of water for microbial growth is expressed by water activity (aw) and DM content can be used as indirect indicator of the water availability. The relationship between DM content and water activity demonstrated decreasing water activity when DM concentration in the crop was increased (Vetra, 1996). Silages with very low dry matter content are often associated with increased seepage losses and clostridial fermentation while very dry ensiled forages do not compact properly resulting in a lower aerobic stability. Optimal dry matter level for ensiling alfalfa depends on environmental conditions and type of silo used. Ishler et al. (1992) recommended that alfalfa should be ensiled at 30 to 35, 35 to 40 and 45 to 60% dry matter when using bunker, tower, or O₂ limiting

storage system, respectively.

Effects of Chopped Length of Forage

The effect of chopping may lead to faster LAB fermentation and therefore to less organic matter losses. The level of particle size reduction affects the silage fermentation in terms of bacterial activity in a crop. Chopping causes a more available substrate and water released from damaged forage cells, resulting in an increased fermentation rate of silages (Pauly & Lingvall, 1999). Chopping of forage usually increases the numbers of LAB (McDonald *et al.*, 1991). The size of forage chopped will give high impact on the effectiveness of the silage formulated. Besides that, it also depends on the type of forage taken as a raw material. Herrmann *et al.* (2011) indicates that chopping at harvest as a mechanical treatment reduces the particle size for enhanced manageability of crop material and for better process conditions at ensiling and feeding. Another aspect of reduction of particle length of forage is seen in relation to the degree of forage compaction. More finely-chopped forage is easier to consolidate the forage in the silo as compared to plant material with a longer-chop length.

Effect of Fermentation Period

Quality silage is achieved when the fermentation process completed well. It occurs when lactic acid is the predominant acid produced, and thus will drop the silage pH quickly. The faster the fermentation is completed, the more nutrients will be retained in the silage (Schroeder, 2004). Table 2 present the different mechanisms occur in fermentation process. It shows that fermentation period is a crucial parameter in producing good silage and each phase must be completed and handled well to get good silage. Normally, 60 days of fermentation period will make it safe, but the effect of longer or shorter fermentation must also be considered to save the time, cost and optimize the nutrient content in the silage.

Silage additives

The use of silage additives seems to be the most important factor to improve the quality and aerobic stability of silages. Carbohydrate additives are most useful in crops that are low in WSC. In a study on molasses as silage additives, Bureenok *et al.* (2011) found ruzigrass silages treated with 5% molasses had lower pH and

higher lactic acid content than control (without molasses). The combined addition of LAB and 2% molasses could enhance the account of desirable *Lactobacillus* and inhibit the growth of undesirable microorganism such as *Clostridia* and *Enterobacter* in soybean silage (Ni *et al.*, 2017). Jian *et al.* (2017) suggested that adding molasses could improve fermentation quality of silage.

Enzymes are also added to forage during ensiling. It degrades non-structural carbohydrates into soluble carbohydrate which act as substrate for microbial fermentation. Enzymes are most needed in low WSC crops such as legumes (Nadeau *et al.*, 2000). Nadeau *et al.* (2000) showed that the addition of cellulases to alfalfa at ensiling increased WSC content, which led to improved ensilability. Guinea grass silage treated with 0.1% of cellulase resulted in best fermentation quality of tropical grasses silage (Khota *et al.*, 2016).

Propionic acid and formic acid are applied to improve aerobic stability of silage as their applications inhibit the growth of spoilage microflora. Study was conducted to evaluate the effect of lactic acid bacteria and propionic acid on the fermentation quality and aerobic stability of whole-crop corn based total mixed ration (TMR) silage. The findings suggested that propionic acid is compatible with lactic acid bacteria inoculants, and when used together, although they reduced lactic acid production and improved aerobic stability of TMR silage (Lei *et al.*, 2016).

Conclusion

Ensiling is a suitable and promising technique for preserving fresh forage with minimal losses which ensures animal feed availability during dry or winter season. Ensiling technology has increased the feeding value of silages. This process is based on lactic acid fermentation under anaerobiosis which preserves the forage in high nutritional value.

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Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Additional information

No Additional information is available for this paper.

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